

Ecuador first CLEWs approach of the electricity sector focus in Climate Change Policies

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2025

Context, Challenges, and Main Findings

- Country: Ecuador
- Population: Aproximately 17M
- Area: 283,561 km²
- GDP: 118,8 billion dollars
- Electricity matrix of Ecuador depends of in hydroenergy (80-90%)
- The NDC comitment is reduce 8% of the GHG emisions in 2025
- The GHG goal may be compromised by climate change

Scenarios definition

- Research question: What are the alternatives for Ecuador to achieve its climate change goals under water restrictions scenario in its hydro energy power plants?

Scenario Label	Key Assuptions
BASELINE	Electricity sector planning, 80% to 90% percent of renewable energy index for electricity generation in the grid Maintain natural gas, and fuel oil power plant running to stabilize the electricity system
HYDRO	Ecuador reduces face a reduction of 62% of reduction in its capacity factor of hydro power energy plants and cover this gap with Light and heavy Fuel Oil Power Plant
LT LEDS	Increases the electricity consumption in 12% due to transition to electric transport and strengthen biofuels consumption. Emission restriction in the same rate as the NDC.

Energy results (PJ)

- HYDRO: 20% of the demand is cover by LFO and HFO
- LTS: 12% of Electricity is covered by solar PV
- LTS: Maintain hydro generation due to high amount of investments

Land use analysis

- Forest Reduction in all scenarios due to development
- Biofuels and Solar PV requires $\approx 300 \text{ km}^2$
- Translate in 30% of coffee crops land requeried projection in 2050

Conclusions

It can be observed that Ecuador's high dependence on fossil fuels may lead to an increase in their use within the electricity generation mix in a water restriction scenarios.

LTS Scenario shows that solar energy emerges as the most cost-effective option, primarily due to Ecuador's current limitations in securing a reliable supply of natural gas.

Increase GHG initiatives through biofuels and solar energy could have a significant impact, especially when compared to the projected use of smaller-scale crops.

Future Work

The results solar pv and biomass (sugarcane) requirements of land use should be analysed at regional level with a more detailed CLEWs model, taking account that the location for each commodity will be different in terms land categories.